

RECYCLING POST-CONSUMER
FIBRES FROM WOOD
WASTE INTO NEW INSULATION
PRODUCTS

OVERVIEW

Wood fibre thermal insulation materials are used in the building envelope to balance indoor temperatures, reduce energy consumption, and improve comfort. In the form of panels, they are produced by compressing wood fibres under heat, combined with adhesives and additives where needed to meet performance targets, including fire safety. In addition to reducing energy use, they improve acoustic comfort and support moisture regulation, offering an efficient biobased, and renewable material for building insulation.

APPLICATION

These products are available in different shapes and types. Rigid panels are commonly used in roofs, walls and floors, both for new builds and renovations. Flexible mats are installed between studs or rafters in timber wall frames, pitched roofs and internal partitions. Loose fill is used to fill cavities and irregular spaces, including wall cavities and attic areas, and is often installed by blowing.

ACHIEVEMENTS

The incorporation of recycled fibres from post-consumer fibreboard and solid wood waste into insulation products was successfully demonstrated at pilot scale (bridging lab and industrial scale). Fibres from two different EcoReFibre technologies have been used: the “modified thermo-mechanical pulping (mTMP)” developed by the Dresden Institute for Wood Technology (IHD) and the “wet process” developed by Dieffenbacher.

Rigid insulation boards showed differences by product density and fibre source. In all cases, high-density boards (200kg/m³) did not reach the required mechanical performance when recycled fibres were incorporated. In contrast, lower-density boards (115kg/m³) met the specifications with up to 25% fibres from post-consumer fibreboard or with well sorted and cleaned fibres from post-consumer solid wood at 25%, 50% and 100% substitution.

Flexible insulation boards with up to 50% fibres from post-consumer fibreboard had properties comparable to conventional reference panels, with even a slightly improved thermal performance. While recycled fibres increase dust content in the board, the addition of a facing on one side could help limit dust release. Flexible insulation boards with up to 100% well sorted and cleaned fibres from post-consumer solid wood met all specifications.

Loose fill insulation was assessed using 25% fibres from post-consumer fibreboard while fibres from post-consumer solid wood were tested up to 100% incorporation.

For attic insulation, none of the formulations met specifications at the incorporation rates tested. For wall cavities, results were more promising with several products meeting the density and thermal conductivity specifications thresholds.

NEXT STEPS

Key next steps include maintaining consistent input quality and tighter process control, especially when using fibres from post-consumer fibreboard to reduce dust and maintain mechanical performance. Lastly, these improvements will need to be confirmed at industrial scale to support process scale-up.

CIRCULARITY

As a renewable, bio-based, carbon storing material, wood is a key driver of Europe's circular bioeconomy. Recycling post-consumer wood waste into insulation products helps extend the lifespan of wood while offering high-quality envelope materials for buildings. Through recycling, carbon is stored and dependence on virgin wood is reduced.

An innovative waste sorting line and smart recycling technologies enable end-of-life fibreboard and solid wood waste to be broken down into fibres, which are then reintegrated into wood-based insulation products. Pilot trials have shown that insulation boards can incorporate high shares of recycled wood while achieving performance similar to reference products. From an economic perspective, increasing recycling can help broaden the raw material base and support stabilising volatile virgin wood prices. Of course, also investments in recycling equipment and process adaptation are required for industrial-scale production. By fostering a circular value chain, from waste sorting to panel manufacturing, the EcoReFibre project contributes to the objectives of the Green Deal, in particular the Ecodesign for Sustainable Products Regulation (ESPR), and supports the goals of the Circular Economy Action Plan (CEAP), while aligning with the upcoming Circular Economy Act (CEA).

IMPACT

As part of its circular bioeconomy efforts, Soprema currently uses about 18% of bio-sourced and recycled raw materials in its global production, mainly for insulation, where recycled content can reach 100% in some products. Within EcoReFibre, the company focuses on **diversifying its raw material sources and increasing the share of recycled wood by addressing the technological challenges of incorporating recycled fibreboard across its wood-based insulation portfolio.**

KEY PRINCIPLES OF CIRCULAR BIOECONOMY INCLUDE:

- Designing products that minimise waste
- Multi-actor dialogue
- Improving resource and energy efficiency
- Using by-products and secondary raw materials
- Promoting awareness and social engagement

ECOREFIBRE CLOSES THE MATERIAL LOOP THROUGH:

- New and adapted technologies & methods
- New collaborations
- New and adapted infrastructure
- Lifecycle analysis
- Supportive regulations and standards
- New business models

CONTACT

SOPREMA

Cestas, France

Laurent Bedel

Insulation R&D Director

lbedel@soprema.fr

 [Soprema on LinkedIn](#)

 soprema.com

SLU SWEDISH UNIVERSITY OF AGRICULTURAL SCIENCES

Uppsala, Sweden

Stergios Adamopoulos

Professor, Wood Science

stergios.adamopoulos@slu.se

 [SLU on LinkedIn](#)

 slu.se

 [EcoReFibre on LinkedIn](#)

 ecorefibre.eu

PARTNERS

Photo credits: Soprema, InnovaWood. Layout: Fovéa création.

This document reflects the authors' views only and neither the Agency nor the Commission are responsible for any use that may be made of the information contained therein.

**Funded by
the European Union**